

Utilization of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) in Araling Panlipunan: It's Relationship to the Learning Competencies Development of Pupils

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ABSTRACT

This paper determined the extent of utilization of MTB-MLE in Araling Panlipunan and will answer answered the following questions (1) What is the extent of utilization of MTB-MLE in Araling Panlipunan as observed by teachers along language development, cognitive development, academic development and socio-cultural development?; (2) What is the level of observed learning competencies development of pupils in Araling Panlipunan?; (3) Is there a significant relationship between the teachers extent of utilization of MTB-MLE in Araling Panlipunan and their observed learning competency development of pupils' most essential learning competencies?; (4) What factors influence the utilization of MTB-MLE in Araling Panlipunan? ; (5) What training design maybe proposed based from the result of the study?

The respondents of the study were 108 teachers in Grade 1- 4 who are handling Araling Panlipunan in 20 schools, at Tinambac South District, considering the distance and geographical location of each school, 70% was the retrieval rate which resulted to 75 teacher respondents, with the following breakdown 20 Grade 1 teachers, 19 Grade 2 teachers ,18 Grade 3 teachers and 18 Grade 4 teachers respectively. Fifty (50) teacher respondents were also interviewed using the interview guide prepared by the researcher. The study used a concurrent mixed method of research. The DepEd Order No. 16, series 2012, was adopted in gathering quantitative data for the extent of utilization and the Most Essential Learning Competency (MELCS) in Araling Panlipunan for the 1st quarter. Interview guide questions were utilized for the factors that influence the utilization of MTB-MLE in Araling Panlipunan.

The following were the conclusions of the study: (1) The utilization of MTB-MLE in Araling Panlipunan obtained all mean rating indicating a "very-high" level of utilization. Academic

development and Language development were found to be a “very-high” level and Socio-cultural development and Cognitive development were given a “high” rating. (2) The learning competencies development in Araling Panlipunan of Grade 1-4 pupils were given a “high” rating.(3) Test of relationship between Mother Based-Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) showed no significant relationship with the Most Essential Learning Competency (MELCS) of pupils .(4) Qualitative instrument showed that, the factors influencing the utilization of MTB-MLE are Availability of teaching materials, Student confidence and speaking skills, Selection of teaching materials and Transition as medium of instruction. A training design was proposed by the study based on the result of the study.

Keywords: MTB-MLE; Education; Learning Competencies; Teachers; Araling Panlipunan

INTRODUCTION

Effective use of language is vital in developing the learners understanding of the lesson and concepts being thought. With the used language in school, learners can better express their thoughts and ideas, support thorough understanding between and among the teachers and learners using the language which can easily be understand. Moreover, with the changing time and a high for the quality education, effective and efficient teaching strategies should be implemented from the first stage of schooling in order to strengthen the foundation. One of these strategies is multilingual education program with it's goal to help students acquire the necessary cognitive and reasoning abilities so that they can communicate effectively in a variety of languages, beginning with their mother tongue.

Multilingual education based on the mother tongue (MTB-MLE) starts with students' knowledge (UNESCO 2015). Language enables the students to adapt successfully with complete confidence, it helped them build a solid foundation in their first language for listening, reading, writing, and other topics. Academic terms used in school are usually learned with a second language or even in different languages to which students are exposed. Children can create a solid foundation and a solid bridge with mother-based multilingual education (MTB-MLE), which will help their effective learning in school (Malone 2017). Using indigenous languages alongside English as the primary language of instruction in all subjects at any level of education will not only change the long-standing denigration of native language, it will also significantly strengthen the status of indigenous languages by enhancing student achievement. The children can exercise their right to study with their mother tongue (Sumbalan, 2017).

Filipino learners face various barriers in education and one of these barriers is that our learners begin their schooling in a language which they do not comprehend. They do not understand the language being used as a medium of instruction in the classroom. The use of mother tongue enables the young learners to immediately construct and explain without fear of making mistakes, articulate their thoughts and add new concepts to that which they already knew. In turn, the teachers can more accurately assess what has been learned and identify the areas where they need help. Now that mother tongue (first language) has been used as a medium of instruction in Kindergarten to Grade 3 for almost six years, negative and positive effects on the pupils' performances in various learning areas within the use of English alone can be minimized. The performance of the students in English, specifically their reading, speaking, listening, and writing skills, may be greatly improved by way of adapting the mother-tongue-based multilingual education in the acquisition of English learning competencies of the Grade school learners (Tadeo, 2020).

The Department of Education (DepEd) has enacted policies in recent years that are pertinent to the current language-in-education policy. The DepEd Order No. 74 issued in 2009 institutionalized Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB MLE) nationwide and mandated the use of the learners' mother tongue (MT) in improving learning outcomes from Kindergarten to Grade Three (DepEd, 2012). The DepEd Order No. 16 issued in 2012 indicated the starting school year of the implementation, which was the school year 2012-2013 and ordered all public schools to adopt it as part of the K-12 Basic Education Program. This order also included objectives emphasizing the four developments that MTB MLE would greatly influence specifically: (1) language development, (2) cognitive development, (3) academic development, and (4) sociocultural awareness. With the MTB MLE's implementation, two modes stipulated in the guidelines were expected to be carried out: (1) mother tongue as a subject area, and (2) mother tongue as a medium of instruction in all learning areas excluding Filipino and English, in kindergarten to grade three levels (DepEd, 2018).

In the Philippines, one of the recent changes in Basic Education Curriculum brought about by the new K-12 program is the introduction of Mother Tongue- Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) specifically in Kindergarten, Grades 1, 2 and 3 to support the goal of "Every Child- A- Reader and A –Writer" by Grade 1." Mother Tongue is used as a Medium of Instruction (MOI) for Grades 1, 2 and 3 in teaching Math, Araling Panlipunan (AP), Music, Arts, Physical Education and Health (MAPEH) and Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao (EsP). Mother tongue is taught as a separate Learning Area in Grades 1 and 2, and since the implementation of this three-year old language policy, it had been coupled by researches justifying its need in the Philippine educational system. One of these researches on the implementation of the MTB-MLE in the Philippines is conducted by Balce(2017) recommending an adoption of the mother tongue (L1) as the language of learning and instruction (LOLI) for Science and Health at the elementary school level for two reasons: (1) The science process skills (or thinking skills) are linguistic: communicating, classifying, inferring, predicting, interpreting data, hypothesizing, defining operationally, and investigating. These skills are best developed and sharpened using the mother tongue. (2) Elementary school children are at a stage in which they are still mastering their mother tongue. They need time to focus and attain the full mastery of their mother tongue to understand complex science concepts.

With the use of mother tongue in classrooms, young learners will be able to understand what the teacher is saying because the medium of instruction is the language that they are familiar with. Hence, the pupils will be comfortable in participating in the classroom discussion and other activities. Young children are eager to learn especially when they have the confidence in themselves for they can communicate freely with the use of mother tongue (Analupa,2019).

The Department of Education has decided to select only the most important and essentials for the School Year 2021-2022 and the most essential learning competencies (MELCS) needed in all subjects that includes Araling Panlipunan. Mother tongue is in its third year of implementation and there are many issues to consider. Teachers are one factor affecting the implementation of the mother tongue teaching. Teachers are an integral part of the Department of Education, the largest agency in the Philippine government with about half a million teachers and support staff. The department administers and supervises both the public and private elementary/primary and secondary schools which are referred to as the two levels in basic education. It is "a complex learning organization that develops, promotes, provides, and ensures basic education responsive to the internal, external, and emerging learning needs" (DepEdClick, 2021)

However, since its implementation, it has been facing several issues and criticisms. For instance, the challenges on how to implement it such that it is aligned with the desired mother-tongue approach (Eslit, 2017) and the challenge implied by Lartec (2017) to the Department of

Education to initiate a mechanism wherein the teachers' innovative strategies and problems are assessed, monitored, and evaluated. The interpretation and implementation in the classroom define the success of the enactment of the policy; what happens on the ground level will contribute either directly or indirectly to the successful implementation of the language policy. It is in this premise that this study was anchored on.

The past years of implementing MTB- MLE in Tinambac South District, teachers experienced challenges like the availability of teaching materials, orthography, and the suitability of the materials to the students' spoken language and the time allotted to the subject. This study would like then to find out the utilization of the mother tongue in teaching Araling Panlipunan subjects to address the current gaps in MTB-MLE implementation for the nation's fundamental education and its effect on the pupil's performance. Specifically, the preferred research location is Tinambac South District because no studies yet have been conducted with the same problem in the district.

Research Questions

The study determined the relationship between the extent of utilization of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) and the level of observed learning competencies development of pupils in Araling Panlipunan in Tinambac South District.

Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What is the extent of utilization of MTB-MLE in Araling Panlipunan?
 - a. Language development
 - b. Cognitive development
 - c. Academic development
 - d. Socio-Cultural development
2. What are the observed level of pupils' learning competencies development in Araling Panlipunan as observed by their teachers?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of utilization of MTB-MLE in Araling Panlipunan and their observed learning competencies development of pupils?
4. What factors influence the utilization of MTB-MLE in Araling Panlipunan?
5. What training design may be proposed based on the result of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study is a descriptive research that used, qualitative and quantitative data. Pearson - r correlations were used for data analysis. The descriptive part of the study was on the extent of utilization of MTB-MLE in Araling Panlipunan and on the learning competencies of pupils along the most essential learning competencies including factors influence that utilization of MTB-MLE. Correlational method was used to determine if there is significant relationship between the extent of utilization of MTB-MLE and the most essential learning competencies of pupils. Qualitative analysis was used to determine the factors influence the utilization of MTB-MLE.

The population of 108 Grade 1 to 4 teachers from 20 schools in Tinambac South District, who used mother tongue as a medium of instruction in the academic year of 2022-2023 constituted as respondents of the study.

Population of the Study

The total population of teacher was 108 but the total retrieval was only 70% which is 75 total population due to the location of the schools and the teachers response towards the survey-

questionnaire. Meanwhile, the population from grade 1 to 4 was 20 Grade 1 teachers, 19 Grade 2 teachers, 18 Grade 3 teachers and 18 Grade 4 teachers respectively.

Instrumentation

For data collection of the study a modified survey questionnaire on the basis or organized according on the given objectives of MTB-MLE in Araling Panlipunan and in this include such areas as (1) language development (2)cognitive development (3) academic development and (4)socio-cultural development. A modified Likert scale was used for measuring responses that would indicate level of utilization of MTB-MLE and extent of competencies development of the learners. The Likert scale ratings will indicate if the respondents Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree. The second part of the analysis was on the Most Essential Learning Competencies of Grade 1 to 4 students in Araling Panlipunan. The rating scale used will be indicative of being Least Evident, Moderately evident, Much Evident and Very Much Evident.

Reliability test was administered to determine the reliability of the questionnaire. To assess the significance of the reliability, Cronbach's Alpha was used taking 15 respondents who were not part of the target respondents. Reliability tests on Language development with 5 items has mean rating indicative of "excellent", Cognitive development with 5 items has mean rating indicating "good" result, Academic development with 6 items has "excellent" result Socio-cultural development with 5 items has a "excellent" interpretation.

On the other hand, interview guide question were meant to identify the factors influence the utilization of MTB-MLE, it's perceived influence on the students' learning. The learner's development of confidence, problem encountered and suggestions on how the MTB-MLE implementation could be made better.

Prior to the distribution of research instrument, approval letter was sought from the Dean of the Universidad de Sta. Isabel Graduate School and also from the study and to the Schools Divisions Superintendent of Camarines Sur for the conduct of the study. Approved letter was presented to the Public Schools District Supervisor and endorsed to the School Head of Tinambac South District to seek permission for the distribution of research instrument. Upon Approval, research instrument was distributed to the schools of Tinambac South District and retrieval of questionnaire was done after given period of time.

For the individual interviews, this was carried out in a conversational manner in order to secure certain trust and unhesitating responses from the participants.

The data gathered were analyzed using descriptive statistics like frequency and mean in order to find out the normative level of MTB-MLE utilization and the most essential learning developed among the grade school learners.

Correlation analysis was done by using Pearson-r coefficient of correlation to determine the significance of association between MTB-MLE utilization and the most essential learning competencies achieved among the grade school learners.

Hypotheses of the Study

There is a significant relationship between the extent of utilization of MTB-MLE in Araling Panlipunan and most essential learning competencies of pupils.

RESULTS and DISCUSSIONS

Table 1

Extent of Utilization of MTB-MLE in Araling Panlipunan along Language Development

INDICATOR	MEAN	Interpretation
<i>Introduce learners to the basic concept of family, community and the region they are belong to speak and understand</i>	3.39	Very High
<i>Learners are able to speak what they learned in Araling Panlipunan using Mother Tongue by letting them to share to the class.</i>	3.37	Very High
<i>Teaching Araling Panlipunan by using simple words helps the learner easily understand the context.</i>	3.36	Very High
<i>Teaching Araling Panlipunan using the Mother Tongue of instruction helps learner to share his/her own learnings.</i>	3.25	Very High
<i>There is a smooth transition of languages in teaching the concept of family, community and region.</i>	3.04	High
Over-all Mean	3.28	Very High

Table 1 shows the extent utilization of MTB-MLE along language development of grades 1-4 pupils in Tinambac South District is summarized in Table 1. Analyzed data revealed “Very High” (3.78) extent of utilization level of MTB-MLE in Araling Panlipunan and language development. The use of MTB-MLE in the said learning areas was perceived as “very high” particularly in making the pupils learn basic concepts of the family, community and the region they were belong (3.39).It was also perceived as “very high” in the effort of letting the pupils speak

using mother tongue in Araling Panlipunan (3.37). “Very high” utilization was likewise seen in the teachers efforts to use simple and easy-to-understand words and statements (3.35) ; including the use of mother tongue in the said areas of learning competencies (3.25). Only with the efforts of language transition, or in trying to find the somewhat close, if not in the right, equivalent words or description in teaching the concepts of family, community and region that certain inconvenience seems to have been experienced by the teachers in their teaching of Araling Panlipunan. Hence this area of concern is was only seen as “high” (3.04) by the teacher respondents. This particular finding, therefore appears to suggest itself that there is still the used for teachers orientation in the different languages that they use for teaching. A sufficient knowledge of the languages used will be enable them to secure the desired extent of MTB-MLE utilization in teaching Araling Panlipunan in their respective schools.

Table 2

Extent of Utilization of MTB-MLE in Araling Panlipunan along Cognitive Development

INDICATOR	MEAN	Interpretation
<i>The use of mother tongue supports learning of the important features of the community they are residing.</i>	3.33	Very High
<i>Using the Mother Tongue in teaching Araling Panlipunan learners express themselves clearly and develop ideas</i>	3.32	Very High
<i>When teaching Araling Panlipunan, Higher Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) was incorporated by asking questions that will stimulate them to dig into deeper..</i>	3.23	High
<i>Through teaching Araling Panlipunan using the Mother Tongue builds a solid foundation of the concept of family, community and region through fostering cognitive abilities and academic subject understanding.</i>	3.17	High
<i>Learner's developed multilingualism using</i>	3.16	High

Mother Tongue in teaching Araling Panlipunan contributed to cognitive flexibility and varied thought.

Over-all Mean	3.24	High
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Table 2 shows is the extent of utilization of MTB-MLE in Araling Panlipunan along cognitive development. Based on the results, the extent of utilization of MTB-MLE in Araling Panlipunan along cognitive development is “high,” with a mean of 3.24. There was “very high” level of usefulness of the MTB-MLE in cognitive development along important features of the community (3.33). Another “very high” level of usefulness of MTB-MLE was in enabling the grade school learners to express themselves clearly and developing ideas (3.22). On the other hand, when it comes to stimulating the learners to Higher Order Thinking Skills (HOTS), a somewhat lower mean (3.23) merely indicating only “high” level of usefulness. The same “high” utility level of (3.17) was also obtained from the MTB-MLE usefulness for building a solid foundation of the concept of family, community and region. And another “high” utility level (3.16) was seen in the MTB-MLE usefulness in developing multilingualism and cognitive flexibility among learners. It appears therefore, that is on these three aforesaid concerns that some bind of reinforcement through teachers retraining are needed for them to equipped with the needed preparation and skills for stimulating learners using mother tongue towards their cognitive development.

Table 3

Extent of Utilization of MTB-MLE in Araling Panlipunan along Academic Development

INDICATOR	MEAN	Interpretation
<i>Speaking skills is developed by letting the learners share in the discussion about family, community and region where they belong.</i>	3.41	Very High
<i>Reading skills will be developed more by providing contextualized reading material that is grade appropriate and to develop a more engaging strategies in reading.</i>	3.41	Very High

<i>Listening skills improves continually with the help of contextualized materials about family, community and region in listening like audio files.</i>	3.39	Very High
<i>Writing skills must be developed by letting write and draw about their own family, community and region</i>	3.33	Very High
<i>The learners develop mastery of competencies in in Araling Panlipunan when they be able to make outputs about their family, community and region.</i>	3.29	Very High
<i>The use of local language through the mother tongue will facilitate teaching and learning in Araling Panlipunan.</i>	3.28	Very High
Over-all Mean	3.35	Very High

Table 3 shows the extent of utilization of MTB-MLE in Araling Panlipunan along academic development. Based on the results, the extent of utilization of MTB-MLE in teaching Araling Panlipunan along academic development, is “very high,” given it’s mean of 3.35. Analyzed data revealed specifically “very high” level of usefulness in developing speaking skills in Araling Panlipunan through discussion about the family, community and region (3.41)in developing learners reading (3.41) and listening skills (3. 390 through contextualized reading materials that are grade appropriate and using mother tongue. “Very High” utility level of (3.33) of MTB-MLE using mother tongue was observed in the learners writing and drawing skills and subjects that deals with family, community and region. Mastery of learning competencies and also is “very high” utility level (3.29) of MTB-MLE using mother tongue in Araling Panlipunan; and language skills development also relates itself to “ very high” utility level of MTB-MLE with mother tongue used for instruction about the family, community and region.

Findings suggest that teachers in the Tinambac South District who are teaching Araling Panlipunan are quite capable of evaluating student performance and learning with a variety of methods used for adapting their instruction to the needs, abilities, and learning preferences of students.

Table 4

Extent of Utilization of MTB-MLE in Araling Panlipunan along Socio-Cultural Development

INDICATOR	MEAN	Interpretation
<i>The use of Mother Tongue as a medium of instruction in Araling Panlipunan gave a strong sense of identity of the community and region they belong.</i>	3.27	Very High
<i>Teaching Araling Panlipunan in Mother Tongue helps learners know the duties and responsibilities of the members of the community</i>	3.24	High
<i>Speaking one's mother tongue in teaching the Araling Panlipunan, fosters pride in one's origin, language, and culture.</i>	3.24	High
<i>In teaching Araling Panlipunan using Mother Tongue protects and preserve the regional</i>	3.23	High

languages and cultures.

Learners learn their own folktales, folk music, and other things in using mother tongue across teaching the academic subjects effectively.

3.20

High

Over-all Mean	3.23	High
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Table 4 shows the extent of utilization of MTB-MLE in Araling Panlipunan along socio-cultural development. Based on the results, the extent of utilization of MTB-MLE in teaching Araling Panlipunan along socio-cultural development is “high,” with its over all mean of 3.23. The results also showed that, the use of Mother Tongue as a medium of instruction in Araling Panlipunan gave a strong sense of identity of the community and region they belong (3.27). Teaching Araling Panlipunan in Mother Tongue helps learners know the duties and responsibilities of the members of the community (3.24). It also fosters pride in one's origin, language, and culture (3.24) and this may ensure itself the protection and preservation of regional languages and cultures (3.23). MTB-MLE with mother tongue used in Araling Panlipunan enables the learners to learn their own folktales, folk music and dance and their cultural elements (3.20)

Among the indicators of the extent of utilization of MTB- MLE in Araling Panlipunan along socio-cultural development, “very high” (3.27 level of utility of MTB-MLE with mother tongue used in teaching Araling Panlipunan was seen in its influence on the learners development of their sense of identity with the community and the region where they belong.

Results revealed that there is pressing issues on why now a days young generation is not aware of what they should have and what they should do to contribute to the betterment of the society. With the advancement in technology we should also return to the basic one and further strengthen it. It is timely that from the grassroots of education the rules, duties and responsibilities and the identity that they have must be will taken into account. The nations stability should begin in the identity that they should know and carried out. Although mother tongue is helpful to the better understanding and learning, but we should take into account that knowing one's nation is the foundation of all and will let you better share of who and what you are. Socio-cultural development should be given emphasis to our young generations so that we could build a strong nation.

Table 5

Summary of the Extent of Utilization of MTB-MLE in Araling Panlipunan

INDICATOR	Mean	VD
Academic Development	3.35	Very High
Language Development	3.28	Very High
Cognitive Development	3.24	High
Socio-Cultural Development	3.23	High
Over-all Mean	3.27	Very High

Presented in Table 5 is the summary of the extent of utilization of MTB-MLE in Araling Panlipunan in Tinambac South District. Base on the results, of extent of utilization of MTB-MLE in Araling Panlipunan has the over-all mean of 3. 27, which indicates a “very high” utility. The extent of utilization of MTB-MLE in Araling Panlipunan along academic development has the highest mean of 3. 35, which also indicates a “very high” utility level. The language development also showed “very high” utility level (328) ,Cognitive development and socio-cultural development with a mean of 3.24 and 3.23 respectively, merely indicated having “high” utility.

The findings show that the teachers used of MTB-MLE in teaching of Araling Panlipunan have its most noticeable on academic development and language development. This would suggests that then teachers in Tinambac South District, regardless of the subject they taught, have integrated native language and used this effectively in their classroom instruction. What appears as needing some improvement are those that have do with cognitive development and socio-cultural development.

Table 6

Observed Level of Pupil’s Learning Competencies Development in Araling Panlipunan of Grades 1

INDICATOR	MEAN	Interpretation
<i>Natutukoy ang mga mahahalagang pangyayari at pagbabago sa buhay simula isilang hanggang sa kasalukuyang edad gamit ang mga larawan at timeline.</i>	3.10	High

<i>Nasasabi ang batayang impormasyon tungkol sa sarili: pangalan, magulang, kaarawan, edad, tirahan, paaralan, iba pang pagkakakilanlan at mga katangian bilang Pilipino.</i>	3.05	High
<i>Naipagmamalaki ang sariling pangarap o ninanais sa pamamagitan ng mga malikhaing pamamamaraan</i>	3.05	High
<i>Nakapaghihinuha ng konsepto ng pagpapatuloy at pagbabago sa pamamagitan ng pagsasaayos ng mgalarawan ayon sa pagkakasunod-sunod</i>	3.05	High
<i>Naihahambing ang sariling kwento o karanasan sa buhay sa kwento at karanasan ng mga kamag- aral at sa ibang miyembro ng pamilya gaya ng mga kapatid, mga magulang (noong sila ay nasa parehong edad), mga pinsan, at iba pa; o mga kapitbahay</i>	3.00	High
<i>Naipagmamalaki ang sariling pangarap na ninanais sa pamamagitan ng mga malikhaing pamamaraan.</i>	2.95	High
Over-all Mean	3.03	High

Analyzed data in Table 6 revealed “high” (3.03) pupils competencies achieved in Araling Panlipunan using Mother Tongue language of instruction in Grade 1 (Table 6). The “high” learning competencies (3.10) was particularly observed in the development of learning ability to know the important changes in life from to present age with the use of pictures and timeline. “High” learning competence (3.05) was also noted in learning the basis of personal information that includes: name, age, parents, birthdate, and other personal of ethnic identification of Filipino as race of people. “High” learning competence was likewise shown in being proud of what could one aspires for and achieve by way of creative and productive works. Learning competence of the learners (3.05) was also seen on the ability to discern the concept of continuity and change by arranging pictures according to their suppose order of relationship. Finally , Grade 1 pupils showed learning

competence to learn the comparative similarity of experiences and life of other individual to one's own (3.00); and also ones similarity of experiences and life to those of the other members of the family , relatives or other persons in the neighborhood (2.95). The preceding findings affirm the basic reason in providing the curriculum guide of the Department of Education.

That the use of simple and easy to understand words facilitate the learning process among the grade school learning. Hence the Department of Education (DepEd) issued Department Order No. 28, s. 2013 that demands from kindergarten through grade three, all subject areas will be taught in the learners' first language, with Filipino and English being taught as separate topics (Department Order No. 74, s. 2009).

Table 7

**Observed Level of Pupil's Learning Competencies Development
in Araling Panlipunan of Grades 2**

INDICATOR	MEAN	Interpretation
<i>Naipaliliwanag ang kahalagahan ng 'komunidad'</i>	3.26	High
<i>Naipaliliwanag ang konsepto ng komunidad</i>	3.21	High
<i>Natutukoy ang mga bumubuo sa komunidad : a. mga taong naninirahan b: mga institusyon c. at iba pang istrukturang panlipunan</i>	3.21	High
<i>Nailalarawan ang panahon at kalamidad na nararanasan sa sariling komunidad</i>	3.21	High
<i>Naisasagawa ang mga wastong Gawain/pagkilos sa tahanan at paaralan sa panahon ng kalamidad</i>	3.16	High
<i>Nailalarawan ang sariling komunidad batay sa pangalan nito, lokasyon, mga namumuno, populasyon, wika, kaugalian, paniniwala, atbp.</i>	3.11	High

<i>Nakaguguhit ng payak na mapa ng komunidad mula sa sariling tahahan o paaralan, na nagpapakita ng mga mahahalagang lugar at istruktura, anyong lupa at tubig, atbp.</i>	3.11	High
<i>Naiuugnay ang tungkulin at gawain ng mga bumubuo ng komunidad sa sarili at sariling pamilya</i>	3.00	High

Over-all Mean	3.16	High
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Presented in Table 7 are the learning competencies of grade 2 pupils along Araling Panlipunan. Analyzed data showed the learning competencies of grade 2 pupils along Araling Panlipunan is “high” (3.16). The teacher respondents using MTB-MLE with Mother Tongue as a medium of instruction have also observed noticeable changes in the learning competence of the Grade 2 learners. As indicated by the tabulated data, the learners could fairly explain the importance of a community to the families and people residing in the area (3.26). They could well present that the basic composition of a community, like residing people, institutions and other social structures. They have also learned to illustrate the effects of weather and calamities experienced by their own community (3.21). The needed responses, works and actions at home and the schools in times of calamities can also be cited by the Grade 2 learners (3.16). Other learning competencies observed to have been fairly achieved include: describing their own community based on its name, location, community leaders or officials, population, language, beliefs and others (3.11); observing simple map of the community starting from their home or schools showing important places and structures, land features and water sources (3.11); and lastly, they are also able to compare the works and responsibilities of the community officials to their own selves and their families (3.00).

Preceding the findings are fairly supportive of the DepEd Order that demanded Mother Tongue-Based MTB-MLE to be implemented in all school, institutions especially in the grade schools (DepEd Order No. 28 series 2013). As could be gleaned from tabulated data, the MTB-MLE, has indeed shown working in the development of learning competencies of the grade school learners and this is a condition suggested enough for sustaining the implementation of MTB-MLE.

Table 8

**Observed Level of Pupil's Learning Competencies Development
in Araling Panlipunan of Grades 3**

INDICATOR	MEAN	Interpretation
<i>Naipaliliwanag ang kahulugan ng mga simbolo na ginagamit sa mapa sa tulong ng panuntunan (ei. Katubigan, kabundukan, etc)</i>	3.50	Very High
<i>Naipapaliwanag ang wastong pangangasiwa ng mga pangunahing likas na yaman ng sariling lalawigan at rehiyon</i>	3.50	Very High
<i>Natutukoy ang mga lugar na sensitibo sa panganib batay sa lokasyon at topographiya nito.</i>	3.44	Very High
<i>Nasusuri ang kinalalagyan ng mga lalawigan ng sariling rehiyon batay sa mga nakapaligid ito gamit ang pangunahing direksiyon (primary direction)</i>	3.33	Very High
<i>Natutukoy ang pagkakaugnay-ugnay ng mga anyong tubig at lupa sa mga lalawigan ng sariling rehiyon</i>	3.33	Very High
<i>Nakagagawa ng payak na mapa na nagpapakita ng mahahalagang anyong lupa at anyong tubig ng sariling lalawigan at mga karatig na lalawigan nito</i>	3.28	Very High
<i>Natutukoy ang mga lugar na sensitibo sa panganib batay sa lokasyon at topographiya nito.</i>	3.22	Very High
<i>Nakabubuo ng interpretasyon ng kapaligiran ng sariling lalawigan at karatig na mga</i>	3.22	Very High

<i>lalawigan ng rehiyon gamit ang mapa</i>	3.11	High
<i>Nasusuri ang iba't ibang lalawigan sa rehiyon ayon sa mga katangiang pisikal at pagkakakilanlang heograpikal nito gamit ang mapang topograpiya ng rehiyon</i>		
Over-all Mean	3.33	Very High

Presented in Table 8 are the learning competencies as observed by the grade 3 pupils using MTB-MLE in Araling Panlipunan. Based on the obtained data “very high” learning competencies were observed among the Grade 3 pupils in the subject of Araling Panlipunan. “Very high” level of learning competence was shown by the learners in practically almost all areas of learning skills. Their ability to explain the meaning of symbols with the help of symbols with the help of signages was quite noteworthy (3.50). They were also able (3.50) to explain the needed management and protective care over the major resources and natural wealth in one’s own province and region. There was notable learning competence (3.33). Observed among pupils in involving the place of the province in one’s own region based on primary direction from its location. Most notable learning competence (3.44) was likewise observed among Grade 3 pupils in their ability to know the places which have potential risks for disaster in view of its topographic conditions. Similarly, the pupils learning competence were also seen (3.28) in their ability to come up with interpretation of the ecological conditions of one’s own province and also more of the neighboring provinces of the region with given map used. A somewhat lower mean (3.11), but still at “high” level of learning competence was seen in the learner’s ability to know the geographic characteristics and conditions of the different provinces.

Table 9

Observed Level of Pupil’s Learning Competencies Development in Araling Panlipunan of Grades 4

INDICATOR	MEAN	Interpretation
<i>Nakapagmumungkahi ng mga paraan upang mabawasan ang epekto ng kalamidad</i>	3.61	Very High
<i>Natatalakay ang konsepto ng bansa.</i>	3.50	Very High
<i>Natutukoy ang mga hangganan at lawak ng teritoryo ng Pilipinas gamit ang mapa</i>	3.39	Very High

<i>Nakapagbibigay ng konklusiyon tungkol sa kahalagahan ng mga katangiang pisikal sa pag-unlad ng bansa</i>	3.39	Very High
<i>Nasusuri ang ugnayan ng lokasyon Pilipinas sa heograpiya nito</i>		
<i>Natutukoy ang relatibong lokasyon (relative location) ng Pilipinas batay sa mga nakapaligid dito gamit ang pangunahin at pangalawang direksyon</i>	3.33	Very High
<i>Nailalarawan ang pagkakakilanlang heograpikal ng Pilipinas:</i>		
<i>(a) Heograpiyang Pisikal (klima, panahon, at anyong lupa at anyong tubig) (b) Heograpiyang Pantao (populasyon, agrikultura, at industriya)</i>	3.28	Very High
Over-all Mean	3.40	Very High

A “very high” level (3.40) of learning competencies in Araling Panlipunan using MTB-MLE system of instruction have been most notably observed among the Grade 4 pupils in the research area (Table 9). “Very high” learning competence (3.61) among the Grade 4 learners in their ability to suggest or recommend ways in order to reduce the effect of natural calamities due to climate change. They would also understand and explain the concept of a nation (3.50). The ability to identify the boundary and extent of the Philippine territory with the use of a map was also observed (3.39). “Very high level (3.39) of learning competence was likewise seen in the learner’s ability to give their conclusion on the great importance of the country’s physical and geographic features to its own development and progress. Another most noticeable (3.33) pupils learning competence was in their ability to explain the relationship of the country’s geographic location with its neighboring countries. Similarly, Grade 4 learners have also demonstrated their ability (3.28) to identify the country’s relative location based on the surrounding things serving as primary and secondary direction. Finally, the learners are also able (3.28) to show the important geographic features of the Philippines, particularly in terms of: (a) geographic physical concerns, like climate, weather, land and water resources; and (b) human resources, land and other physical establishment and social structures e.g. population, agriculture, industry and other institutional structures.

Table 10

Summary of the Observed Level of Pupil’s Learning Competencies Development in Araling Panlipunan of Grades 1-4 pupils

INDICATOR	Mean	VD
Grade 4	3.40	Very High
Grade 3	3.33	Very High
Grade 2	3.16	High
Grade 1	3.03	High
Over-all Mean	3.23	High

Presented in Table 10 is the summary of the observed level of pupils learning competencies development of Grade 1 to Grade 4 pupils in Araling Panlipunan using Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education system of instruction. Base on the results, the learning competencies of Grades 1 to Grade 4 pupils in Araling Panlipunan obtained an over-all mean of 3.23, which indicates a “high” learning competence.

The data showed that there was only “high” level of learning competencies observed among the learners from Grade 1 to Grade 4 pupils who have undergone MTB-MLE with Mother tongue used for teaching Araling Panlipunan. In terms of grade level, however, both Grade 3 and Grade 4 obtained mean learning competence level of 3.33 and 3.40 respectively, which are indicative “very high” learning competence on the other hand, Grade 1 and Grade 2 pupils obtained mean competence of 3.03 and 3.16 respectively, which are merely indicative of “high” learning competence level. These findings leave us the question-why the Grade 3 and Grade 4 pupils have shown much better competencies than the learners of Grade 1 and 2?.The answer maybe lying on the their differences of learning experiences , that in terms of acquired concepts, vocabulary and knowledge- the relatively nature upper grade pupils are likely to have much better edge than their younger lower grade level counterparts.

Table 11

Relationship Between the Extent of Utilization of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education and the Most Essential Learning Competency

Aspects	Pearson Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)	Interpretation
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Language Development	.226	.052	Not Significant
Cognitive Development	.129	.269	Not Significant
Academic Development	.224	.053	Not Significant
Socio-Cultural Development	.142	.225	Not Significant

The correlation test, using Pearson r , on the extent of utilization of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) and competency in all areas of essential learning revealed no significant association between the said variables (Table 11). The test of relationship, for instance showed no significant link ($r=0.226$) between MTB-MLE utilization and language development. Cognitive development is not also significantly related ($r=0.129$) with MTB-MLE utilization. Likewise academic development is not statistically significant ($r=0.224$) with MTB-MLE utilization. The same findings off insignificant relationship was obtained between MTB-MLE utilization and socio-cultural development.

The findings suggest is that MTB-MLE has no significant bearing on the learner’s learning competency development. Apparently, the learners learning competencies development would have been attributed to factors other than the MTB-MLE utilization. These factors may include the learner’s exposure to media, their access to internet via mobile phone, the parents or other family members assistance to their school children, and other factors outside the school. What these findings them imply is that there is still a lot more to be done for MTB-MLE utilization its’ to be effective and to be sustained as a system of classroom instruction.

Factors that Influence the Utilization of MTB-MLE

Based on the data obtained from the interview of the teacher respondents regarding the factors influencing the utilization of MTB-MLE resources ($n=50$), the following issues were identified.

Limited Teaching Materials/Resources

For the first core idea, 24 respondents (out of 50) claim that students are confused in using some terminologies. Even the teachers are struggling ($n=13$). Teaching materials are limited ($n=11$). The following are some of the responses:

“Some resource materials are not available and outdated” (TR8, 2023)

“Kulang po ang resources para po sa pagtukdo kan Mother Tongue ” (Not enough resources for total integration of technology in the class especially during the pandemic) (TR11, 2023)

“There are words that has no translation in MTB-MLE learners find it hard to understand the thought’s” -(TR15, 2023)

“ The problem in using MT as medium of instruction in teaching AP, some pupils don't understand MTB because their L1 is Filipino, therefore teachers should be flexible at all times” -(TR19, 2023)

These statements affirm that teachers' resources are limited and might affect the classroom instruction in using mother tongue in Araling Panlipunan. Also, the variables available learning resources are inadequate for the use of pupils. Thus, some teachers result to using teaching materials that are not updated or materials that do not have correct translation. This observation is supported by the findings of Lartec et.al. (2018) who stated that some problems encountered by the teachers in implementing mother tongue-based instruction include absence of books written in mother tongue, lack of vocabulary, and lack of teacher-training.

Student's Gain more Confidence and Develop their Speaking Skill

Another key finding of this study was students gained more confidence and developed their speaking skill (n=14), despite having scarcity on teaching materials the teachers was able to inculcate the learning competencies of mother tongue along Araling Panlipunan. Some statements attesting to these were:

“ Gamit ang Mother Tongue sa pagtukdo ning Araling Panlipunan mas nahiling ko sa mga akin a mas madali saindang magparticipate asin nagsasabi kan saindang nasa isip” (Using MTb learners in teaching Araling Panlipunan confidently share his/her knowledge ideas and experiences in the class) (TR32, 2023).

“ MTB-MLE is of great help to the learner to gain more confidence and develop their speaking skill” (TR25, 2023).

“Learners show more confidence in conceiving and explaining content and more articulate in expressing their ideas , explain without fear of committing mistake and add new concept to those they already know”. -(TR2, 2023)

“ Madali nindang nasasabi toltol ang nasa isip ninda” (It easier to the learner to express themselves). -(TR7, 2023)

“ Since they use their own dialect, it helps to speak and express their thoughts in a particular topic in Araling Panlipunan”. -(TR15, 2023)

“ They can participate in class discussion and can express their ideas and thoughts' using their MT”. -(TR29, 2023)

“ Boosts their confidence in engaging in class discussion”. -(TR36, 2023)

“Mother Tongue aided the learners development of confidence hence it based from their local experiences they easily expressed themselves”. -(TR44, 2023)

These statements affirm that teachers have their positive observation on teaching Araling Panlipunan using the MTB-MLE. Despite the lack of teaching materials, the teachers were able to teach their students effectively by using the native language of Tinambac. Children learn better and more quickly in a language they can understand (preventing learning delays), which is one of the advantages of an education that considers children's mother tongues. They feel more at home and like they are enjoying school more. Students often display more self-esteem. When children use their multilingualism, they may benefit from higher socioeconomic status, including higher earnings. On the average, the schools perform better, reporting less repetition and less drop-out. Parents can assist their children in the homework and can participate in school activities.

Selecting Teacher Teaching Material/Resources

Another key finding of this study was on selecting teacher teaching material/resources (n=11). Teachers claimed that an appropriate teaching materials for teaching mother tongue along Araling Panlipunan is of much help for classroom instruction.

Based on the statements of the teachers, some suggested that:

“ I would suggest that MTB-MLE implementation could be made better if not all subjects areas apply it like in Math and Science”. – (TR1,2023)

“ Ang guro sana dapat dumaan sa mga trainings para madaling maimplement ang MTB-MLE sa pagtuturo ng Araling Panlipunan”. (Teachers must undergo in several seminars/workshops training in MTB-MLE so that it is easy to adopt and implement MTB-MLE in teaching AP).– (TR11,2023)

“ Implementation of MTB enable the learners use different language for success in school and for lifelong learning-1. Read aloud and encourage learners to bring books to share and explain or translate 2. Read mote stories 3. Watch movies and shows 4. Teach them rhymes and poems”. –(TR48,2023)

“ Since implementing/integrating MTB-MLE is a spiral progress, I suggest that if there are pupils who are already understand the subject matter, I suggest that we need to help them proceed with the higher thinking skills and to not them wait for other pupils who are just learning in progress because for me they are unfair to those learners who are advance, waiting for those pupils who are slowly learning”. –(TR26,2023)

“ Provide learning materials with appropriate use of language (in MTB-MLE).Like for example (in Bikol central) the textbooks should be written in Central Bikol language also words found in textbooks”. –(TR17,2023)

“ There should be a dictionary in MTB so that there is a basis in writing the correct words and spelling”. –(TR10,2023)

“In Grade 1 using MTB-MLE is an effective in teaching and I would suggest that it will not be removed or subject to be removed in the curriculum in the future, because it has a big help in teaching other subject specially in Math”. –(TR4,2023)

Transition of Language as Medium of Instruction

Other key findings of this study was the difficulty experienced by the teachers in shifting the medium of instructions since in Grade 4, teachers are using second language in teaching Araling Panlipunan (n=15), that's why they retain the Mother Tongue in teaching. The following are the respondents' challenges/problems and suggestions:

“ One of the problems/challenges in teaching Araling Panlipunan with the use of MT is that , during the transition of learnings from Language 1 to Languagev 2 down to language 3, as they continue more complex concepts in higher grade levels”(TR49 2023)

“There should be a standard MTB-MLE in discussion. We should not mix words from different localities to avoid misconceptions” (TR9 2023)

“In grade 4, we use second language as medium of instruction. Using the first language will hinder them acquire the 2nd language and express ideas.It should be used as a medium of instruction in all subjects especially Mathematics and Science. Teaching language for an easy translation of understanding and improvement of learners vocabulary can be done by MTB-MLE subject alone with using it in other subjects” (TR20 2023)

“Filipino is the medium of instruction I am using in grade IV. I am using mother tongue to explain the lesson. The problem and challenges is pupils behavior and unavailable technology equipment's”(TR50 2023).

“There is no question about using MTB-MLE in the implementation of this particularly in teaching Araling Panlipunan subject. I think doing this is called translanguaging. If I may offer guidance on its implementation I suggest that teachers should continue applying this because somehow it has a positive impact on students learning. Using contextualized learning materials and interactive to be more engaging and interactive teaching strategies and using educational technologies I believe would lead in having a positive learning outcomes” (TR16 2023)

“Grade IV pupils is having difficulty because this is the period of transition, I always see to it that second language should be used for them to be prepared when they reached the higher grades” (TR21 2023)

“Para sakuya ang medium of instruction sa pagtukdo AP dapat Filipino pa din gagamiton sana an bikol kung may mga tataramon na nasasakitan an mga estudyante asin para mas maintindihan ninda ang leksyon. Ini para din mapreparar sinda pag nag nataas na an saindnag grado o kun mag mag lipat sinda nin eskwelahan.”(TR 30 2023)

Transitioning from language 1 to language 2 is the main key factor to be considered in teaching Araling Panlipunan. In the Philippines however, there is a very diverse population with different local dialects and the flexibility of the teacher therefore in the use of local language should always be considered and will be taken in to for the effective learning of students. Furthermore effective transition will not take effect immediately and will take some time, therefore the teachers and parents should provide assistance to the students. Transition is part of the process so it should be embraced whatever it may take.

The factors indeed influencing the utilization of MTB-MLE are as follows; limited teaching materials and inadequacy for student use. The learning competency of the students did not meet achieve the desired level. The students nonetheless gained more confidence and developed their speaking skill, because of the teachers resourcefulness in the making of some teaching materials that meet the expected learning competency in MTB-MLE. The teacher then can chose teaching material best suited to the skills of the students and the needed transition of language for classroom instruction.

Training Design to Strengthen MTB-MLE along Araling Panlipunan thru Project STRENGTH (Strategies, Techniques Revisitation in Education to Gain the Holistic Development of Pupils)_- MTB-MLE in AP

Rationale

The proposed Training Design is based on the findings of the study which showed that the teachers in Tinambac South District experienced lack of materials/resources in teaching Araling Panlipunan using MTB-MLE. There is, thus the need to assess and make some adjustment of the materials for MTB-MLE instruction. The teacher-respondents suggested for the need to undergo some training for teaching Mother Tongue along Araling Panlipunan and to make a contextualized material. This training aims to further strengthen the integration of Mother Tongue in teaching Araling Panlipunan of elementary teachers of Tinambac South District that will assure effective teaching strategies, techniques and tools. The strategies include the teacher’s continuing effort of researching and developing contextualized materials. Moreover, the strategies should aim to provide teachers with a variety of teaching techniques and strategies through the use of various technology-based teaching materials. A quality operational framework supporting new teaching techniques and tools must also be considered for MT-MLE instruction.

Objectives

The suggested Training Design intends to:

1. Make an inventory of existing and used teaching strategies techniques and the least learned competencies, determine the best practices and come up with the necessary improvement by determining its reliability.
2. Create context-sensitive resources for the Araling Panlipunan lessons that support the curriculum guide's learning objectives, particularly in raising students' level of learning competency.
3. Equip teachers with a variety of teaching methods and strategies through the use of contextualized resources.
4. Give the teachers the pedagogical tools they need.
5. Let the teachers evaluate their progress on how they taught Araling Panlipunan with the use of mother tongue.

TARGET PARTICIPANTS

The target participants of the training are Teachers of Tinambac South District teaching Araling Panlipunan using mother tongue as medium of instruction. Specifically, they are the teachers from Grade 1 to 4.

TARGET DATES

Target date of the training is between the weeks before the opening of School year 2023-2024 which falls on last week of August 2023.

Conclusions

The extent of utilization of MTB-MLE in Academic and language development is "very high" while along Cognitive development and Socio-cultural development, "high"

Very high level of competency development was obtained from Grade 3 and Grade 4 pupils while high level was noted for Grade 1 pupils.

All computed value r - values were found significantly lower than the critical r value level, no significant association exists level of utilization MTB-MLE and competencies development of pupils.

Appropriate learning resource materials are critical in the learning competency development of pupils.

Recommendations

Continuous capability building of teachers should be done in schools. Particularly in the development of learning resource materials considering the desired competencies in Araling Panlipunan.

Teachers can be supported and encouraged to develop appropriate learning resource materials to enhance their competencies and learning competencies of pupils in Araling Panlipunan.

Further study should be conducted along this line for longer period. Study period should be extended to effectively evaluate competency development of pupils.

Teachers can be supported in terms of capacity building and learning resources development for more effective learning competencies development of pupils.

Measurable indicators for all learning competency must be considered in further studies.

Learning resource materials development on MTB-MLE in the required subject areas should be given financial allocation.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The research instrument was distributed with a cover letter, that explains the purpose of the study and that the participation is voluntary and with personal consent form for the would be respondents or participants to sign on for approval, in compliance with Republic Act 10173. Participants were also informed that their responses will be treated with absolute confidentiality.

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